

THE ROLE IN THE PLANT AND THE FUNCTIONS OF NUTRIENTS

Saitkulov Foziljon Ergashevich¹

Ibragimov Bo'ronboy Olimjon o'g'li²

Allaqulova Muxlisa Baxrom Qizi³

Umarov Samandar Farhod o'g'li⁴

Xolmatova Mohigul Olimjon Qizi⁵

¹Tashkent State Agrarian University,

²⁻³⁻⁴⁻⁵Student of Tashkent State Agrarian University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7450935>

Annotation: Macro and microelements are necessary for plants in the largest amount, as they are components of many plant components, including proteins, nucleic acids and chlorophyll, and are important for such physiological processes as respiration, maintenance of osmotic pressure.

Key words: Macronutrients - N Nitrogen, P Phosphorus, K Potassium, • Mesoelements - Ca Calcium, Mg Magnesium, S Sulfur, Trace Elements - Fe Iron, Mn Manganese, B Boron, Zn Zinc, Si Copper, Mo Molybdenum, Cl Chlorine.

INTRODUCTION

One of the fundamental laws in ecology - Liebig's Law of Minimum — states that the most significant factor for an organism is the one that most deviates from its optimal value. Therefore, during the prediction of environmental conditions or the performance of examinations, it is very important to determine the weak link in the life of the organism.

Liebig found that the productivity of cultivated plants, first of all, depends on the nutrient (mineral element) that is most poorly represented in the soil. For example, if the P of Phosphorus in the soil is only 20% of the required norm, and the Ca of Calcium is 50% of the norm, then the limiting factor will be the lack of phosphorus; it is necessary first of all to introduce Phosphorus fertilizers into the soil.

A figurative representation of this law is named after the scientist — the so-called "Liebig's barrel". The essence of the model is that when filling the barrel, the water begins to overflow through the smallest board in the barrel and the length of the remaining boards no longer matters.

METHOD AND RESULTS

Basic data on the nutrient requirements of all green spaces rarely change. It is well known that 16 different elements are necessary for the proper and calm growth of plants and their development from seed to maturity. Three of these elements – carbon, oxygen and hydrogen – are obtained by plants directly from the environment, and the remaining 13 must be provided with soil, fertilizers or various organic materials.

Each of the nutrients plays its own specific role, therefore they are called essential, i.e. no other element can replace them. Some of them can jointly affect the development of the plant, but only partially. One example of such cooperation is potassium and sodium, which can to some extent replace each other when exposed to sugar beet.

In addition to sunlight, carbon dioxide, oxygen and water, thirteen essential nutrients for plant growth are considered. They are divided into:

- Macronutrients - N Nitrogen, P Phosphorus, K Potassium
- Mesoelements - Ca Calcium, Mg Magnesium, S Sulfur
- Trace Elements - Fe Iron, Mn Manganese, B Boron, Zn Zinc, Si Copper, Mo Molybdenum, Cl Chlorine.

Macro- and mesoelements are necessary for plants in the largest amount, as they are components of many plant components, including proteins, nucleic acids and chlorophyll, and are important for such physiological processes as respiration, maintenance of osmotic pressure.

CONCLUSION

The main role of trace elements in plants is that they are part of enzymes that are catalysts of biochemical processes, increasing their activity. The lack of trace elements leads not only to a decrease in yield, causes a number of diseases in plants, and sometimes their death, but also reduces the quality of human and animal food.

Therefore, it is so important to conduct a soil analysis in the Laboratory and determine the content of nutrients in your field. Proper systematic tillage and fertilization of the soil will improve soil fertility and increase crop yields. When applying fertilizers, it is necessary to take into account the characteristics of the soil of the site: the degree of its fertility and availability of nutrients, the mechanical composition of the soil, the reaction of the environment, culture, the age of the plantings.

Literature:

1. Saitkulov F. E. et al. 2, 3-Dimethylquinazolin-4 (3H)-one //Acta Crystallographica Section E: Structure Reports Online. – 2014. – T. 70. – №. 7. – C. o788-o788.
2. Saitkulov F. et al. TITRIMETRIC ANALYSIS OF CALCIUM CATION IN "MEGATON" VARIETY OF CABBAGE //International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 10. – C. 134-135.
3. Sapaev B. et al. Synthesis of 2-methylquinazoline-4-thione with the purpose of alkylation of 3-propyl 2-methylquinazoline-4-thione with alkylating agents

//AIP Conference Proceedings. – AIP Publishing LLC, 2022. – T. 2432. – №. 1. – C. 020009.

4. Boymuratova G. O. et al. To Examine the Processes of Biochemical Action Of 6-Benzylaminopurine with Cobalt-II Nitrate Dihydrate on the “Morus Alba” Variety of Moraceae Plant //Eurasian Journal of Physics, Chemistry and Mathematics. – 2022. – T. 3. – C. 39-42.

5. Sapaev B. et al. Study of methylation reactions of 2-phenylquinazoline-4-tion with “soft” and “hard” methylation agents and determination of its biological activity //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2021. – T. 258. – C. 04023.

6. Saitkulov F. et al. Biochemical nutrition family plant rute-lemon leaved //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 17. – С. 268-273.

7. Usmonovich E. T., Bakhtiyor O’g’li A. S. Study of the Condensation Reaction of Amines Different Environment //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF BIOLOGICAL ENGINEERING AND AGRICULTURE. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 121-123.

8. Ergashevich S. F. et al. Photochemical Processes Photosynthesis Pathway On House Plants Leaves" Black Prince" //Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 10. – С. 76-78.

9. Ergashevich S. F. et al. Photochemical Processes Photosynthesis Pathway On House Plants Leaves" Black Prince" //Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 10. – С. 76-78.

10. Saitkulov F. et al. CHEMICAL FEEDING METHOD OF LEMON PLANT USING LEAF STOMATA //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 17. – С. 274-277.

11. Strutinskii F. Sposoby fizicheskoi obrabotki zerna v kombikormakh // Svinovodstvo. — 1982. — № 8. — pp. 32-33

